

Development of fly ash based geopolymeric cementitious materials for new millennium

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Abstract : The present studies have been carried out with a view to exploit the potential of fly ash from thermal power, Sarni (Madhya Pradesh), India as resource material for making geopolymeric cementitious materials. Sample cubes of 5 cm × 5 cm × 5 cm dimensions of green cementitious material were prepared in the laboratory by alkali activation of fly ash by varying quantity of alkali and sodium metasilicate. Prepared cubes were dried at room temperature and cured at 90 °C in hot air oven for 48 h. Compressive strength of cubes was determined and characterisation of the prepared geopolymeric cementitious materials of three different mix compositions has been done using sophisticated techniques namely X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). Compressive strength is found in the range of 13 to 22 N/mm² for three different mix compositions. Highest compressive strength is observed for Mix 3 and is comparable with 7 days compressive strength of Portland cement which is 22 N/mm² as per IS 269, ordinary Portland cement; 33 grade-specification. The prepared geopolymeric cement free cementitious material will be useful for making cement free concrete for non structural applications.

Keywords : Alternate cementitious material, geopolymers, fly ash, alkali activation.

Introduction

Portland cement is widely used construction material all over the world¹. However, the process of production of Portland cement is highly energy intensive and also releases high amount of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere (one tonne of CO₂ per tonne of cement) which is responsible for global warming^{2,3}. In order to address such problems, there is an urgent need for development of energy efficient green materials which use less natural resource and energy and generate less CO₂ and can be used as an alternative to conventional cementitious materials⁴. Among the developed materials, 'geopolymeric materials' gains increasing attention, which are aluminosilicate materials formed by alkali activation of solid aluminosilicate raw materials⁵. In comparison to ordinary Portland cement, geopolymers can be produced at room temperature and releases no green house gases during their production and can also be prepared from industrial by-products containing alumina and silica thus helps in

environment management⁶. Apart from this, desired functionality can be developed in geopolymeric materials by varying the composition and type of source materials used, as it has been established that the nature and composition of the source materials have significant effect on properties of geopolymers⁷.

In the present studies, synthesis of geopolymeric cementitious materials has been reported by alkali activation of fly ash using different quantities of alkali and binder.

Results and discussion

Compressive strength of sample cubes as shown in Table 1 reveals that highest compressive strength is observed for Mix 3. It is comparable with 7 days compressive strength of Portland cement which is 22 N/mm² as per IS 269, ordinary Portland cement; 33 grade-specification. Increase in compressive strength is observed with increase composition of alkali as well as binder from Mix 1 to Mix 3. This is due to increase in release of aluminate

Table 1. Quantity of raw materials used and compressive strength for cubes of dimensions 5 cm × 5 cm × 5 cm

Mix	Fly ash (g)	Alkali (g)	Binder (g)	Compressive strength (N/mm ²)
1	100	10	5.0	13–15
2	100	15	7.5	15–17
3	100	20	10.0	20–22

and silicate species from amorphous silico aluminous phases of the fly ash. Similar results were also observed by others⁸ indicating that increase in alkali concentration results in greater solubility of source material.

X-Ray diffraction analysis of fly ash and Mix 1, 2 and 3 are shown in Fig. 1. Comparison of X-ray diffraction pattern of fly ash with standard JCPDS data⁹ indicating

Fig. 1. X-Ray diffractogram of fly ash, Mix 1, 2 and 3.

the presence of quartz, SiO₂ (hexagonal, JCPDS file number 33-1161), mullite, Al₆Si₂O₁₃ (orthorhombic, JCPDS file number 15-776) and hematite, Fe₂O₃ (Rhombohedral, JCPDS file number 33-664) phases. Some of the peaks in fly ash due to quartz, hematite and mullite disappeared in Mix 1, Mix 2 and Mix 3. Details of peaks of fly ash that disappeared in Mix 1, Mix 2 and Mix 3 are shown in Table 2. The disappearance of these peaks of quartz, mullite and hematite phases of fly ash in different Mixes is due to the reaction of these phases with strong alkaline solution during geopolymerisation.

Fig. 2 presents IR spectra of fly ash and Mix 1, 2 and 3. Peak assignments in IR spectra are given in Table 4. The band around 1091 cm⁻¹ in fly ash due to Si-O-Si and Al-O-Si asymmetric stretching vibrations shift towards higher wave number in IR spectra of Mix 1, 2 and 3 alongwith appearance of several small new peaks indicating formation of new material due to dissolution of amorphous aluminosiliceous phase of fly ash in strong alkali solution¹²⁻¹⁴. The small sharp band around 1628 cm⁻¹ due to OH bending vibrations and broad band at 3448 cm⁻¹ due to Si-OH vibrations in IR spectra of fly ash due

Table 2. Peaks of quartz (Q), mullite (M) and hematite (H) phases of fly ash disappeared in X-ray diffraction pattern of Mix 1, 2 and 3

Sr. No.	Mix 1			Mix 2			Mix 3		
	Q	M	H	Q	M	H	Q	M	H
	<i>d</i> values								
1.	2.27 (8)	1.37 (5)	1.37 (5)	2.27 (8)	1.37 (5)	1.37 (5)	2.42 (3)	2.42 (3)	1.44 (5)
2.	1.97 (5)	1.37 (4)	1.37 (4)	1.97 (5)	1.37 (4)	1.37 (4)	1.97 (5)	1.52 (9)	1.38 (7)
3.	1.37 (5)	1.33 (3)	1.33 (3)	1.37 (5)	1.33 (3)	1.33 (3)	1.44 (5)	1.44 (5),	1.37 (5)
4.	1.37 (4)	-	-	1.37 (4)	-	-	1.38 (7)	1.38 (7)	1.33 (3)
5.	1.33 (3)	-	-	1.33 (3)	-	-	1.37 (5)	1.37 (5)	-
6.	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.33 (3)	1.33 (3)	-

The new peaks appeared at different *d* values in X-ray diffraction pattern of Mix 1, Mix 2 and Mix 3. Details of new peaks appeared are represented in Table 3. The appearance of new peaks are due to formation of sodium silicate, Na₆Si₈O₁₉ (monoclinic, JCPDS file number 18-1239) and sodium aluminium silicate hydrate, Na₂Al₂Si₂O₈.H₂O (orthorhombic, Nepheline hydrate, JCPDS file number 10-460) phases. This changes confirmed formation of aluminosilicate gel network^{10,11}.

to absorbed atmospheric water¹⁵ is replaced by several small peaks in IR spectra of Mix 1, 2 and 3 whereas peak at 2360 cm⁻¹ due to H-O-H stretching vibrations in fly ash remains as such in IR spectra of Mix 1, 2 and 3. The lower frequency region i.e. below 700 cm⁻¹ of fly ash ascribed to symmetric stretching and bending vibration of Si-O-Si, Al-O-Si^{15,16} and O-Si-O undergo changes in Mix 1, 2 and 3 due to chemical reaction of amorphous silico-aluminous phases present in fly ash with alkaline solution and leading to the formation of amorphous to semi crystalline materials. This confirms the reaction between alkali activator solution and fly ash in geopolymeric material.

Table 3. New peaks appeared in X-ray diffraction pattern of Mix 1, 2 and 3

Sr. No.	Mix 1	Mix 2	Mix 3
		<i>d</i> values	
1.	5.41 (18)	5.44 (19)	6.34 (8)
2.	3.08 (12)	3.66 (7)	3.21 (7)
3.	2.65 (18)	3.45 (31)	3.08 (21)
4.	2.46 (9)	2.30 (12)	2.58 (8)
5.	2.30 (15)	1.84 (6)	2.47 (7)
6.	1.70 (7)	1.70 (7)	2.03 (7)
7.	-	1.67 (5)	1.74 (6)
8.	-	1.39 (6)	-

SEM micrograph of fly ash and geopolymer Mix 1, 2 and 3 are shown in Fig. 3. Spherical globules of different sizes with smooth boundaries were observed in SEM of fly ash. These are due to glassy phase present in fly ash. SEM micrograph of Mix 1, 2 and 3 reveals that shape of globules get distorted due to dissolution of amorphous glassy silico-aluminous phase present in fly ash in alkaline solution. This is due to formation of geopolymer gel which increases from Mix 1 to Mix 3. Apart from this,

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of fly ash, Mix 1, 2 and 3.

Table 4. Peaks due to vibrations of different groups in IR spectra of fly ash and Mix 1, 2 and 3

Sr. No.	Fly ash	Mix 1	Mix 2	Mix 3	Peak assignment
			Wave number in cm^{-1}		
1.	1091	1515	1423, 1459, 1516	1458, 1514	Si-O-Si , Al-O-Si asymmetric stretching
2.	1628	1647, 1690	1648, 1698, 1743	1648, 1698, 1742	OH bending
3.	2360	2359	2360	2359	H-O-H stretching
4.	3448	3615, 3677, 3743, 3842	3616, 3647, 3677, 3743, 3852	3616, 3647, 3677, 3743, 3837	Si-OH vibrations

few unreacted crystalline grains were also observed due to presence of unreacted crystalline phases of fly ash namely quartz and mullite which remain inert to considerable extent during geopolymerisation. Quartz acts as a filler and mullite provide reinforcement to the geopolymer matrix.

Experimental

Fly ash collected from Thermal Power Plant, Sarni (Madhya Pradesh), India containing SiO_2 63–65%, Al_2O_3 27–29%, Fe_2O_3 3–4%, K_2O 1–2% and Na_2O , CaO and MgO below 1% is used as the base material in this work¹⁷.

Commercial grade sodium hydroxide, sodium meta-

Fig. 3. SEM micrograph of fly ash, Mix 1, 2 and 3.

silicate and tap water were used to carry out experimental studies.

Specimen cubes of 5 cm × 5 cm × 5 cm dimensions were prepared in the laboratory and used in this tests¹⁸. Compositions used for the preparation of sample cubes are given in Table 1. For the preparation of sample cubes the aqueous solution of alkali and sodium metasilicate were mixed with fly ash to form slurry. Slurry was poured into moulds and sample cubes were dried at room temperature and cured at 90 °C in hot air oven for 48 h. Compressive strength of sample cubes was determined and characterization of the developed material was done using various sophisticated instrumental techniques viz. XRD, IR and SEM.

The X-ray diffraction intensity was recorded as a function of Bragg's 2θ in the angular range of 5–70° on D8 advance X-ray diffractometer to determine different phases. Infra red (IR) spectra was recorded between 4000–400 cm^{-1} using Bruker Alpha Fourier Transform Infra Red spectrometer to determine functional groups present

in the samples and their vibrations. Morphology was determined using JEOL JSM 5600 Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). Strength of cubes was determined using digital compressive strength testing machine model no. AIM 308E-DG of AIMIL Ltd., India.

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